

Using Data Science to Identify Potential Biomarkers of Autistic Spectrum Disorder from Gut Microbiome Samples

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1 Introduction

There is increasing evidence that Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD), a severe neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by abnormal behavioral symptoms (Vuong & Hsiao 2017), is associated with gastrointestinal symptoms (Fulceri et al. 2016). Recent studies have shown that changes in gut microbiota can modulate the gastrointestinal physiology (Powell et al. 2017; Sharon et al. 2016). Thus, in microbiome research the potential role of the gut microbial composition in promoting and reflecting ASD symptoms has become an active line of research (Sharon et al. 2019, Tomova et al. 2020, Li et al. 2019). Along this line, it was found that the gut microbiome of individuals with ASD is different from the gut microbiome of typically developing (TD) individuals (Liu et al. 2019, Coretti et al. 2018, Kushak et al. 2017).

Against this background, in their paper [Altered gut microbial profile is associated with abnormal metabolism activity of Autism Spectrum Disorder](#) Zhou et al. (2020) analysed the gut microbial composition of 143 children with ASD, as compared to 143 TD children without ASD. Methodologically, Zhou et al. (2020) collected microbial DNA from the childrens' fecal samples. Subsequently, 16S rRNA sequencing was used to identify the microbial species in the fecal samples. Their study explores, among other things, the abundance and diversity of the microbiome of children in the ASD and TD groups. In this way, the researchers try to understand whether alternations of the gut microbiome may serve as biomarkers to predict ASD status.

In the project presented in this notebook, data from Zhou et al.'s (2020) paper is explored using the the Python package [Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology 2](#) (QIIME2). The QIIME2 package supports data science methods from bioinformatics, biostatistics and machine learning. The aim of this project is to characterize the differences in the microbiome profiles of the two groups (ASD vs TD) based on the 16s rRNA sequencing data. More specifically, the following analyses are conducted here:

- **Alpha Diversity Analysis:** This type of analysis aims at summarization and description of the composition of microorganisms in the samples in order to better understand microbiome heterogeneity of the samples across groups (see <https://microbiome.github.io/OMA/microbiome-diversity.html>)
- **Differential Abundance Analysis:** This type of analysis aims at detection of differences in taxonomic composition between samples with the aim of identifying microbial species whose abundance counts in samples might serve as biomarkers to distinguish between ASD and TD status (see <https://microbiome.github.io/OMA/differential-abundance.html>).

2 Data

2.1 Data Description

The original data from Zhou et al. (2020) contains 16S rRNA sequencing data from a cohort of 143 children with ASD, as compared to 143 typically developing (TD) children without ASD. 16s rRNA sequencing uses PCR to amplify portions of the bacterial 16s rRNA gene. Upon genomic sequencing of the data, bioinformatical comparisons of the samples to a 16s rRNA reference database are performed, based on which the identified genomic profiles are assigned to the phylogenetic ranks to create a taxonomic profile of the microbiome sample.

The original data from Zhou et al. (2020) is available in the dataset [Gut microbiota analysis associated with autism spectrum disorders \[16S rRNA\]](#). The original raw data contains:

- absolute abundance counts for each of the 1322 microbiome species (termed Operational Taxonomic Unit, OTU) identified by 16s rRNA sequencing in each of the 286 gut microbiome samples (143 ASD children, 143 TD children); data provided as [Excel spreadsheet](#)
- the exact nucleic acid sequence of each of the 1322 OTUs, represented as 254-character strings (e.g. TACGTGG ...)
- sample metadata about each of the 286 children, from which gut microbiome samples were taken.

In order to use Zhou et al.'s raw data in QIIME2, the datasets need to be converted into the QIIME2 format. To ensure reproducibility of the analyses presented here, all preprocessing steps, including downloads from the original web sources, are explained in an interactive notebook that can be followed in a step-by-step manner in the [complementary repository](#). The preprocessing steps yield the following files in the folder `../data/preprocessed`: - `16s_feature_table.qza`: abundance data stored as QIIME2 feature table - `GSE113690_Autism_16S_rRNA_OTU_sequences_preprocessed.qza`: 16s RNA sequencing data - sample metadata

2.2 Data Import

Import 16s rRNA Abundance Data

```
[1]: # make sure plots are shown in notebook cells
      %matplotlib inline

      import seaborn as sns
      from qiime2.plugins import feature_table
      from qiime2 import Artifact

      # feature table
      tab_16s = Artifact.load("../data/preprocessed/16s_feature_table.qza")
```

Import 16s rRNA Sequence Data

```
[2]: # import 16s rRNA sequences
      seq_16s = Artifact.load("../data/preprocessed/
      ↪GSE113690_Autism_16S_rRNA_OTU_sequences_preprocessed.qza")
```

Import Sample Metadata

```
[3]: # import metadata as pd.DataFrame
import pandas as pd

metadata_df = pd.read_csv("../data/preprocessed/sample_metadata.tsv", sep="\t")
metadata_df.drop([0], axis=0, inplace=True)
metadata_df["age"] = metadata_df.age.astype(int)
metadata_df["age_binned"] = pd.cut(metadata_df["age"], bins=[0,3,6,11],
→labels=["2-3", "4-6", "7-11"])
```

```
[4]: # import metadata as QIIME2 object
from qiime2 import Metadata
sample_metadata = Metadata.load("../data/preprocessed/sample_metadata.tsv")
```

3 Data Analysis

A particularly outstanding feature of QIIME2 is its support for interactive data exploration and analysis in interactive plots. Since interactive exploration is incompatible with the static format of this document. To ensure reproducibility of the analyses presented here and to retain their interactive characteristics, all steps of the analyses are explained in an interactive notebook that can be followed in a step-by-step manner (see `analyses.ipynb`).

3.1 Alpha Diversity Analysis

For the phylogenetic diversity analyses, a sampling depth of 31000 was chosen based on the inspection of the feature table summaries. The value of 31000 retains a maximum of features while discarding a minimum of samples.

3.1.1 Principal Coordinates Analysis

A Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) was performed to visually assess similarity of the microbial communities in the two groups based on Jaccard Distance (see Figure 1). The PCoA plot shows three TD clusters (blue) which are relatively close to each other, while the ASD data is more heterogeneously distributed. This suggests that the microbiota composition of the ASD group is clearly different from that of the TD group, and that there is larger within-group variability in the ASD group.

An Analysis of Similarity (ANOSIM) test shows that samples within one group (ASD or TD) are statistically significantly closer (i.e. more similar) to samples from the same group than they are to samples from the other group ($p = 0.001$, $R = 0.229$), thus supporting the visually determined differences between the two groups in the PCoA plot. Group significance plots of the ANOSIM tests are shown in Figure 2:

3.1.2 Shannon Diversity

The Shannon Diversity Index measures the species diversity of each individual's microbiome sample. The higher the index, the higher the diversity; an index value of 0 would mean that only one species is present in the sample (see <https://www.omnicalculator.com/ecology/shannon-index#what-is-the-shannon-diversity-index>).

```
[5]: # compute Shannon Index for each sample
import numpy as np
from qiime2.plugins import diversity
alpha_result = diversity.pipelines.alpha(table=tab_16s, metric='shannon')
alpha_shannon_df = pd.DataFrame(alpha_result.alpha_diversity.view(pd.Series))
alpha_shannon_df["group"] = np.where(alpha_shannon_df.index.str.
    ↳startswith("A"), "TD", "ASD")

# add sample metadata to Shannon indexes
alpha_shannon_df = alpha_shannon_df.merge(metadata_df.iloc[:, [0,3]],
    ↳left_on=alpha_shannon_df.index, right_on="sample-id")

# discretize age variable
alpha_shannon_df["age_binned"] = pd.cut(alpha_shannon_df["age"],
    ↳bins=[0,3,6,11], labels=["2-3", "4-6", "7-11"])

#visualize as boxplot
sns.boxplot(y="shannon_entropy", x="group", data=alpha_shannon_df)
```

```
[5]: <AxesSubplot:xlabel='group', ylabel='shannon_entropy'>
```


The boxplots above show that the ASD group is characterized by higher species diversity than the TD group, which may be associated with the higher within-group variability identified in the PCoA plot above. A Kruskal-Wallis test indicates that the difference in Shannon diversity scores between ASD and TD is statistically significant ($p < 0.0097$, $H = 6.69$).

The below boxplots grouped by age and ASD status show that in the TD group, alpha diversity increases with age, while in the ASD group there is no such increase. Thus, the development of the microbial composition in the ASD group over time is not consistent with the TD group; note that Zhou et al. (2020) also observed in the data that the development of gut microbiota in the ASD group displayed a serious lag.

```
[6]: # visually inspect Shannon Diversity across groups and ages
sns.catplot(y="shannon_entropy", x="age_binned", hue="group",
            data=alpha_shannon_df, col="group", kind="box")
```

```
[6]: <seaborn.axisgrid.FacetGrid at 0x7f40338da220>
```


3.2 Differential Abundance Analysis

Differential Abundance Analysis uses information on the taxonomic ranks of the microbial species found in the samples as well as each species abundance count in order to determine which species' abundances (i.e. absolute frequency counts) differ the most between the ASD and TD groups. Differential Abundance Analysis is used to identify potential biomarkers (see <https://microbiome.github.io/OMA/differential-abundance.html>).

To analyse the taxonomic composition of samples, it is first necessary to assign taxonomic ranks to the 16S rRNA sequences identified in each sample, thus identifying the microbial species in the samples. In this notebook, the taxonomic information from Zhou et al.'s (2020) original paper is used. As an alternative to using the taxonomic information provided in the original dataset, taxonomic information can also be computed directly from the sequence data of the original dataset. This processes of taxonomy assignment to samples is based on a pre-trained Naive Bayes Classifier trained on the [GreenGenes 13_8 OTU reference database](#) - for a reproducible demonstration, the reader is referred to the notebook `preprocess_data.ipynb` of the complementary repository). Note that Zhou et al. obtained the taxonomic information based on the GreenGenes_13_5 rather than GreenGenes_13_8 reference database.

QIIME2 supports interactive visual explorations of the taxonomic composition (see notebook `analyses.ipynb`).

3.2.1 ANCOM

Analysis of Composition of Microbiomes, or ANCOM (Mandal et al. 2015) is used to identify taxa (e.g. phyla, families, species, ...) that are differentially abundant across groups (see <https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ANCOMBC.html>) based on pairwise tests of statistical significance and effect size (see <https://forum.qiime2.org/t/specify-w-cutoff-for-anacom/1844/10>).

Differential abundance can be analysed at any taxonomic level (e.g. phylum, family or genus level)

by collapsing the feature table on the respective taxonomy level. Here, differential abundance analysis at the genus level is demonstrated; in the notebook `analyses.ipynb`, analyses at the phylum and OTU level are performed as well.

The results of an ANCOMA analysis can be visualised as volcano plots

In the Volcano plot shown above, microbiome genera located towards the upper right (high W statistic, i.e. effect size difference of given genus across groups, on the x-axis, and high F score, i.e. strength of ANCOM test statistic, on the y-axis) are likely to be significantly different across groups. Genera in the upper left corner are also statistically significantly different across groups, albeit with lower effect size, therefore they might not be as relevant.

The microbial species at the genus level that contribute most to differential abundance between ASD and TD can be extracted from the ANCOM results table, which provides an alternative to the visual inspection of the volcano plot:

```
[7]: ancom_results_genus = pd.read_csv("assets/ancom/ancom_group_genus/ancom.tsv",
    ↪ sep="\t", index_col=0)
ancom_results_genus["id"] = ancom_results_genus.index
sns.barplot(y="id", x="W", data=ancom_results_genus[ancom_results_genus["Reject_
    ↪ null hypothesis"]==True])
```

```
[7]: <AxesSubplot: xlabel='W', ylabel='id'>
```


At the genus level, the ANCOM analysis identified a total of 10 statistically significant differentially abundant species, with the genus *Ruminiclostridium_6*, *Prevotella_2* and *Alloprevotella* being the three most differentially abundant genera.

3.2.2 Random Forrest Classifier

As an alternative to classical biostatistical tests such as ANCOM, a machine-learning approach is to be employed in order to identify differentially abundant species across AD and TSD children. The QIIME2 package supports machine-learning pipelines for the classification of sample metadata (e.g. group assignment ASD vs TD) from the 16s features. The classifier is trained on 5-fold cross validation with grid-search-based hyperparameter tuning. In this notebook, analyses are performed at the genus level; in the notebook `analyses.ipynb`, Random Forest classifiers at the OTU and phylum levels are computed, too.

At the genus level, the classifier achieves overall accuracy of 96.1% and an AUC score of 0.97. In the ASD group, 95.5% of the samples are classified correctly, and in the TS group 96.6% are classified correctly, thus suggesting strong discriminatory power of the genus level in predicting ASD status.

Feature importance can be used to determine the strongest discriminators. In the figure below, the 25 strongest microbial discriminators at the genus level are shown:

```
[8]: %%capture
      ### Predict ASD vs TD status from microbiomial composition at genus level

      from qiime2.plugins import sample_classifier
      import qiime2.plugins.taxa.actions as taxa_actions

      taxonomy_orig = Artifact.load("../data/preprocessed/16s_rRNA_GSE113690_taxonomy.
      ↪qza")

      table_genus, = taxa_actions.collapse(
          table=tab_16s,
          taxonomy=taxonomy_orig,
          level=7,
      )

      classifier_genus = sample_classifier.pipelines.
      ↪classify_samples(table=table_genus, metadata=sample_metadata.
      ↪get_column("stage"), estimator="RandomForestClassifier", cv=5,
      ↪random_state=123, n_jobs=4, parameter_tuning=True);
```

The most discriminant bacteria genera are analysed based on the classifier's feature importance:

```
[9]: feat_impo_genus = classifier_genus.feature_importance.view(pd.DataFrame)
      feat_impo_genus['genus'] = feat_impo_genus.index.str.extract(r'(g_..+)$',
      ↪expand=False)
      feat_impo_genus
```

```
sns.barplot(y="genus", x="importance", data=feat_impo_genus.iloc[0:25, :])
```

```
[9]: <AxesSubplot: xlabel='importance', ylabel='genus'>
```


From the feature importance plot shown above, it can be seen that the most differentially abundant genus is *Prevotella_2*, followed by *[Eubacterium]_xylanophilum* and *Ruminiclostridium_UCG-014*.

3.2.3 Comparison between ANCOM and Random Forest

ANCOM has identified 10 genera that are statistically significantly differently abundant across ASD and TD. When comparing the ANCOM results with the top-20 features from the Random Forest Classifier, there are 8 genera identified by both methods, which is a considerable overlap and thus suggests that these genera might indeed be truly differentially abundant.

```
[10]: genera_ancom = ancom_results_genus[ancom_results_genus["Reject null_
↳hypothesis"]==True].index.str.extract(r'(g___.+)$', expand=False)
genera_ancom_set = set(genera_ancom)

genera_rf = feat_impo_genus.iloc[0:20, :].index.str.extract(r'(g___.+)$',
↳expand=False)
genera_rf_set = set(genera_rf)

# show genera that were identified by both ANCOM and RF
genera_ancom_set & genera_rf_set
```

```
[10]: {'g__Alloprevotella',
      'g__Comamonas',
      'g__Prevotella_2',
```

```
'g__Prevotella_9',  
'g__Ruminiclostridium_6',  
'g__Ruminococcaceae_UCG-014',  
'g__[Eubacterium]_xylanophilum_group',  
'g__unclassified_f__Enterobacteriaceae'}
```

These candidates may warrant further biological analyses in order to determine their feasibility as biomarkers of ASD status.

4 Conclusions

In this project, it was found that the gut microbiome shows significant differences in terms of diversity between ASD and TD children. Noteworthy, it was found that the development of the microbiome over time of the ASD group is not consistent with the TD group.

Furthermore, two different approaches to differential abundance analysis were employed. In fact, the overlap between the differentially abundant species identified by the two methods was considerable, thus suggesting the potential of these microbial genera as potential biomarkers.

From a methodological perspective, this project highlights the feasibility of data science for the field of microbiome research (Shetty & Lahti 2019, Kyripides et al. 2016). Also, it shows the usefulness of the QIIME2 package: While in this notebook all computational analyses were conducted in QIIME2, Zhou et al. (2020) use a number of tools for the individual steps of the analysis.

References

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